

A hierarchical Framework for Response Times and Signal Detection Theory

Abstract

Signal detection theory is useful in determining the sources of responding error—either in responding bias (over/under selecting responses) or sensitivity. The current work extends signal detection theory by incorporating response times under a unified hierarchical model to provide a richer and more holistic view of multiple response data.

Summary

When assessments begin incorporating more innovative item types, it opens opportunity to collect multiple observations on a single test item. This often begins a psychometric exploration in determining whether there is added value in scoring items polytomously rather than dichotomously. One possible approach to analyze multiple-response (MR) items is using a polytomous IRT model, e.g. Partial Credit Model (PCM). It is possible to think of MR items as having several different combinations of partially correct answer sets to provide some type of an intermediate score between all wrong or all right (dichotomously scored). A simple example of this might be an intermediate category that is a subset of the set of correct responses which would allow for an item with three response categories: all wrong, partially correct, and all correct. Much of the psychometric literature focuses on scoring MR items in this fashion.

Multiple response item types

Figure 1 displays several item types across a range of constraints. Of conventional item types, a two-alternative forced-choice item is one of the most constrained item types. A true-false item is the most widely used two-alternative forced choice. A multiple-alternative forced-choice item type follows and is less constrained. This item type is popularized through the traditional multiple-choice item, whereby examinees select a single option out of several alternatives. A multiple-choice item extends easily to a multiple response item by requiring examinees to select a set number of options. This type of multiple response item is still forced-choice because the item stem specifies the number of options to select. Relaxing this last constraint leads to the multiple alternative unforced-choices item type. Conventionally, this is a multiple response item where examinees may select any number of options from a set. We argue that this item type is best suited to assess the construct of cue recognition, the discrimination between information that is relevant or irrelevant to a decision.

Figure 1. An example of alternative and multiple alternative forced- and unforced-choice alternative items. Items are less constrained when the number of alternatives increases and when their choices are unforced.

Decision-making

Rational decision-making demands gathering information as a prerequisite first step. Whether gathering information physically or retrieving it from long term memory, one needs to determine its relevancy. With simple problems, this process is quick and implicit, and it places little burden on the decision maker. More complex problems, however, present decision makers with an abundance of available information. And because of this, efficiently sifting through information and accurately categorizing its relevancy are both vital.

Whether it is implicit and instantaneous or deliberate and time-consuming, the filtering process described above is a form of cue recognition: one recognizes pertinent information and ignores distractors. Therefore, when faced with several pieces of information, decision makers endorse—recognize—the cues relevant to the current decision task but reject those that are irrelevant (e.g., Pleskac, 2007). Ignoring the seemingly unimportant, they consider only information determined as relevant. This is the information that influences decisions, and therefore, they must make well-calibrated choices.

Choosing to attend to incorrect information leads to inappropriate conclusions or actions. Likewise, considering only partial information can lead to decision errors. And although errors can emerge throughout the entire decision-making process, beginning the process accurately reduces the likelihood of their occurrence in later stages. With two classes of cues, accuracy takes on two forms. In the first class of cues, the valid cues, a correct endorsement is a hit, and failure to endorse a valid cue is a miss. Thus, greater accuracy occurs when decision makers increase their hits and reduce their misses. However, accuracy for valid cues alone is not sufficient; they must consider the other class of cues, the invalid cues. Ignoring an invalid cue results in a correct rejection, whereas endorsing an invalid cue results in a false alarm. The two classes of cues are commonly referred to as signal and noise, and with increased sensitivity to signal, decision makers better discriminate between valid and invalid cues—they properly tease apart signal from noise (see Swets, 2014). Accounting for both types of cues, accuracy increases when maximizing both hits and correct rejections and minimizing both misses and false alarms.

Cognitive psychologists commonly study cue recognition in its most basic form, which allows maximum control over experimental settings. Typically, participants study a list of cues and, after an intervening delay, have their memory tested with a recognition task. The task presents participants with a new list of words, comprising both studied cues (i.e., valid cues) and unstudied cues (i.e., invalid cues) but requires them to select only the studied cues. In other words, participants must endorse only the valid cues and ignore the invalid cues—they perform cue recognition (Pleskac, 2007).

Initially, experimenters scored recognition accuracy by applying a correction method; they subtracted the number of false alarms from the number of hits. Inspecting the endorsement rates of hypothetical participants is the best way to demonstrate the properties of this scoring method. Imagine three participants studied 10 cues and tested over 20 cues, half of which were unstudied. Shown in Figure 2 are the endorsements of hits and false alarms. Participant 1 endorses the most amount of information, correctly identifying all the studied cues but also incorrectly identifying six unstudied cues. The second participant endorses fewer studied and unstudied cues. The last participant endorses the fewest studied cues—less than the other participants—and does not endorse any unstudied cues. The first participant is quite liberal, the second is less so, and the third participant is quite conservative. The dashed line in the figure represents their corrected score. All three participants earn the same score, despite obvious

differences in behavior. The current work seeks to understand whether the differences in responding behavior is systematically related to the speed in which information is endorsed.

Figure 2. The number of valid and invalid cues recognized by three participants. The dashed line is the corrected score calculated by subtracting invalid cues from valid cues.

Signal-detection theory

To better capture behavioral differences, the field adopted a more intuitive analysis, signal detection theory (for a review, see Swets, 2014). Applying the theory of signal detection to recognition memory requires several basic assumptions. In particular, the theory assumes that cues vary across an underlying memory strength and become endorsed when passing a criterion—a minimum threshold. Because studying valid cues increases their memorability, the distribution of memory strengths for valid cues is greater than for invalid cues, which are unstudied. The general model is shown in Figure 3. With greater sensitivity (d' , d -prime), the distance between valid and invalid cues increases. A neutral placement of the criterion (c) is equally distant from the signal and noise distributions, and bias occurs when the criterion is not perfectly centered. Thus, when measured from the center of the two distributions, positive criterion values indicate conservative cue selection; one needs more evidence—more memory strength—to endorse cues. Conversely, negative criterion values indicate liberal cue selection, and cue recognition requires relatively little memory strength to surpass the threshold. A signal detection model accounts for both types of cues, valid and invalid, by estimating sensitivity and bias. This avoids a corrected score that conflates liberal with conservative participants.

Figure 3. An illustration of a signal detection theory applied to cue recognition. The measure d' is the distance between the valid (signal) distribution and the invalid (noise) distribution. The measure c is the distance between the center of the two distributions and the response criterion. One recognizes all cues with memory strengths greater than the criterion.

Multiple response items

To apply the theory of signal detection to multiple response items, we made the assumption that what underlies cue recognition is the strength of a cue's association to the context (i.e., the probe). And although we make no strict theoretical claims, it stands to reason that, much like in basic recognition experiments, candidates monitor a general familiarity of the cue-to-context association. Thus, when the familiarity of a cue's association surpasses a criterion, a candidate makes an endorsement and indicates that the cue is relevant to the context. For example, if asked to select all the symptoms of a disease, candidates select only those that have symptom-to-disease associations more familiar than some lower bound. Candidates with thresholds set too low select all the presented symptoms, regardless of their validity. To them, all the symptoms have a sufficiently familiar association in the presence of the disease; these candidates recognize cues liberally. In contrast, candidates with thresholds set too high select only strikingly familiar symptoms; these candidates are ultraconservative and recognize too few cues.

To specify the signal-detection model, assume the cues are samples from two normal signal and noise distributions with equal variance, the probability of endorsing a cue from the signal distribution is

$$P(y = 1|S) = \Phi((\Psi_S - c)/\tau), \quad (1)$$

such that $y = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if candidate endorses a cue,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$

and Ψ_S representing the mode of the signal distribution, c representing the endorsement criterion, and τ representing a scale parameter (e.g., variance of the signal and noise distributions). Likewise, the probability of endorsing a cue from the noise distribution is

$$P(y = 1|N) = \Phi((\Psi_N - c)/\tau), \quad (2)$$

with Ψ_N representing the mode of the noise distribution and c and τ representing the same criterion and scale parameter. Combining these probabilities, DeCarlo (1998) parameterized a signal detection model in terms of the following generalized linear model:

$$P(y = 1|X) = \Phi\left(\frac{\Psi_N - c}{\tau} + \frac{\Psi_S - \Psi_N}{\tau} X\right), \quad (3)$$

where X takes on the values of 1 for signal cues and 0 for noise cues. Setting Ψ_N to 0 and τ to 1 reduces the model to

$$P(y = 1|X) = \Phi(-c + dX), \quad (4)$$

with d measuring the distance between the noise and signal distribution. As mentioned above, the distance between the two distributions is a measure of a candidate's sensitivity to valid cues; greater distances indicate better cue recognition. However, using the above coding structure for X , the model measures the criterion from the mode of the noise distribution. This complicates interpretation because for the criterion to reflect bias, both signal and noise distributions must be considered. For example, imagine the criterion at a fixed location. As the signal distribution moves further from the noise distribution, the interpretation of the criterion changes. Although the criterion once represented conservative behavior, because of greater separation between the noise and the signal distributions, it now represents liberal behavior. However, setting X to take on the values of .5 for signal cues and -.5 for noise cues results in a model measuring the criterion from the center of the two distributions, accounting for both signal and noise (see Appendix A in DeCarlo, 1998). Now, one interprets the criterion as an indicator of bias, independent of sensitivity.

By extending Equation 4, we have the following signal detection item response model:

$$P(y_{ij} = 1|c_i, d_i, \alpha_j, \delta_j, \mathbf{X}) = \Phi\left(-c_i + d_i \mathbf{X} - (-\alpha_j + \delta_j \mathbf{X})\right). \quad (5)$$

Let y_{ij} indicate endorsement of a cue for candidate i on item j . Candidate parameters c_i and d_i are the bias and sensitivity parameters for candidate i , with positive values of c_i reflecting conservative responding and larger values of d_i reflecting better discrimination between valid and invalid cues. Item parameters α_j and δ_j are the bias and sensitivity parameters for item j . Like the item difficulty parameter in the Rasch model, δ estimates the difficulty of recognizing cues within an item. In addition, α estimates an item's propensity to solicit conservative or liberal behavior from a participant; a biased item results in candidates' overselecting or underselecting its cues, regardless of cue validity. The vector \mathbf{X} contains the indicator variable for cue status.

Response Time

To further understand why individuals are liberal or conservative when making their selections, we extend the SDT framework by incorporating response times. To accomplish this, we model response times under a unified hierarchical framework. This approach models response times and their correspondence to item sensitivity (e.g., item difficulty, inspired by van der Linden, 2007) and their correspondence with responding bias. Both hierarchical frameworks impose a multivariate structure on two sublevel measurement models (SDT and lognormal response time models). Contrasting and comparing parameters from these submodels shows whether sensitivity or responding bias contribute more to an individual's responding behavior.

From an item analysis perspective, this framework identifies items that have a high propensity to solicit slow-liberal, slow-conservative, fast-liberal, or fast-conservative responses. Because each classification implies different types of mental processing, this analysis is useful for evaluating whether an item

measures the intended underlying construct. For example, an item that produces fast-liberal responses might assess a different mental process than an item that solicits slow-conservative responses. Likewise, from a person analysis perspective, this method determines whether a person is more likely to make slow-liberal, slow-conservative, fast-liberal, or fast-conservative responses. Again, because the implied mental processes associated with these responding behaviors are different, this analysis provides a richer description of the underlying mental strategy one uses for an assessment.

The response time model used in this study has the following structural form (see van der Linden, 2007):

$$P(t_{ij}|\tau_i, \beta_j, \gamma_j) = LN(\beta_j - \tau_i, \gamma_j^{-2}). \quad (6)$$

$$t_{ij} \sim LN(\beta_j - \tau_i, \gamma_j^{-2}), \quad (6)$$

where response times t_{ij} are lognormally distributed, β_j represents the labor intensity of an item, γ_j represents the discriminating power of an item, and τ_i represents the processing speed of candidate i . The higher-level models govern the population latent traits and item parameters. They take on the following forms:

$$(c, d, \tau) = MVN(\mu_{cd\tau}, \Sigma_{cd\tau}) \text{ and} \quad (7)$$

$$(\alpha, \delta, \beta, \gamma) = MVN(\mu_{\alpha\delta\beta\gamma}, \Sigma_{\alpha\delta\beta\gamma}). \quad (8)$$

To apply the theory of signal detection to multiple response items, we made the assumption that what underlies cue recognition is the strength of a cue's association to the context (i.e., the probe). And although we make no strict theoretical claims, it stands to reason that, much like in basic recognition experiments, candidates monitor a general familiarity of the cue-to-context association. Thus, when the familiarity of a cue's association surpasses a criterion, a candidate makes an endorsement and indicates that the cue is relevant to the context. For example, if asked to select all the symptoms of a disease, candidates select only those that have symptom-to-disease associations more familiar than some lower bound. Candidates with thresholds set too low select all the presented symptoms, regardless of their validity. To them, all the symptoms have a sufficiently familiar association in the presence of the disease; these candidates recognize cues liberally. In contrast, candidates with thresholds set too high select only strikingly familiar symptoms; these candidates are ultraconservative and recognize too few cues.

However, one class of MR items fall more naturally into an alternative set of response models based on signal detection theory (SDT). Consider, for example, MR items where respondents must select relevant information out of a much larger set. Collapsing across endorsements and rejections creates a single measure of accuracy, which is what item response theory models rely on. However, a single measure of accuracy is not sufficient when investigating recognition based cognitive phenomena (i.e., recognizing relevant from irrelevant content; Rouder & Lu, 2005; DeCarlo, 2011). Individuals might be inaccurate because they have poor discriminability or because they have a responding bias (over/under endorsing information). For this reason, measuring and teasing apart sensitivity and endorsement bias make signal detection a useful measurement model for this class of innovative MR items. This allows for evaluating the response bias of an individual by identifying whether they tend to over select relevant options, known as liberal responders, or under select, known as conservative responders. This information expands on the type of information one would get from a polytomous IRT model.

To further understand why individuals are liberal or conservative when making their selections, we extend the SDT framework by incorporating response times. To accomplish this, we model response times under two different hierarchical frameworks. The first approach models response times and their correspondence to item sensitivity (e.g., item difficulty, inspired by van der Linden, 2007) and the second approach models response times and their correspondence with responding bias. Both hierarchical frameworks impose a multivariate structure on two sublevel measurement models (SDT and lognormal response time models). Contrasting and comparing parameters from these models show whether sensitivity or responding bias contribute more to an individual's responding behavior.

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Methods and Findings

A set of over 40 MR items have been exposed in field tests for a licensure/certification exam with an expected minimum sample size of 2000 exposures per item. All items will be evaluated using a hierarchical SDT model incorporating response times. Parameters are estimated using stochastic methods with reasonable priors and starting points.

The field test data has been collected and is in the process of being merged for psychometric analysis. Although exploratory analyses indicate sufficient power for detecting differences in responding behavior, the complete analysis is planned to be carried out within the next two months. We believe the results will provide evidence to support prior findings in SDT along with insights into how SDT can help to provide important information over-and-above that information provided by IRT models.

Practical Implications

The practical implications of this research will provide practitioners with exposure to a number of different methods for evaluating MR items. Many psychometricians will have their first exposure to a SDT model that provides interesting information beyond basic IRT model parameters. Moreover, with the addition of the response times to SDT, there is opportunity to provide unique feedback to subject matter experts when reviewing and evaluating how items function. Finally, these findings will provide the first example of an analysis of real field test data using a hierarchical SDT model that has been proposed.

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